

PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT NEEDS OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS IN ALILEM DISTRICT: INPUT FOR A LOCALIZED FRAMEWORK IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FACULTY DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Professional development plays a crucial role in enhancing the knowledge, skills, and competencies of elementary teachers. This study aims to identify the professional development needs of elementary teachers and provide input for the development of a localized framework in the implementation of faculty development. A comprehensive review of literature was conducted to explore the specific areas of professional development that are essential for elementary teachers. The findings highlight the importance of professional development in areas such as content knowledge and pedagogy, technology integration, classroom management and behavior support, assessment and data analysis, collaboration, and culturally responsive teaching. Additionally, the study examines the preferences and job satisfaction of elementary teachers in relation to their autonomy over professional development. The results indicate that teachers express higher job satisfaction when they have autonomy over their own professional development. The insights from this study provide valuable input for the design and implementation of a localized framework that addresses the unique professional development needs of elementary teachers. By aligning professional development opportunities with these needs, educational institutions can support the growth and effectiveness of elementary teachers, ultimately enhancing student learning outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

The processes and actions that aim to improve teachers' professional knowledge, abilities, and attitudes in order for them to increase students' learning can be referred to as teachers' professional development. After entering the workforce, professional development refers to acquiring new skills through career training and ongoing education. To increase your knowledge in your chosen subject, it may involve enrolling in seminars or workshops, going to professional or industry conferences, or receiving a credential. The concept of professional development acknowledges that development can be offered in a variety of settings, from the formal to the informal, and defines it as "activities that develop an individual's skills, knowledge, expertise, and other characteristics as a teacher."

One of a teacher's main responsibilities is to deliver effective instruction. The teaching profession is always evolving. due to the profession's always evolving and eternal nature. The most important person in the classroom is the instructor. The future of pupils could be either made or broken by their teachers. Professional growth can be improved through faculty development initiatives such lesson planning, lesson delivery, and knowledge of the topic, the teacher's ability to connect with the pupils, and classroom management.

There is an increase in instructional methods in the collaboration and innovation in the twenty-first century (Wirth & Feldmann, 2019). Currently, teachers are well recognized that ongoing professional development is essential for improving teachers' overall effectiveness and increasing their performance and commitment to their work. The contemporary educational system requires teachers to constantly adapt modifications are made to satisfy the needs and demands of students in the worldwide economy. Instructional Planning must be effectively realized to attain positive student outcomes. Instructional plans can make knowledgeable teachers become competent and effective educators who can transform the learner (Cuñado & Abocejo,2019) No Filipino Child Left Behind Act of 2010: The State shall take appropriate measures to ensure that all citizens have access to high-quality education. education is available. Recent changes emphasize curricular consistency, which makes teachers more responsible. As a Since instructors have a significant impact on students, it might be difficult to identify the results that would best show their efficacy and how to evaluate outcomes. The educational attainment of students is significantly influenced by good teachers who have a mastery of the subject matter, appropriate pedagogical training, and a positive attitude toward teaching (Ajayi *et al.*, 2020). A deeper comprehension of has something to do with preparing pupils to be lifelong learners. pedagogy's impact on student learning (Paniagua & Istance,2018). (Ajayi *et al.*,2020) claim that effective teachers with a command of the subject matter, appropriate pedagogical training, and a constructive outlook attitudes toward instruction are important factors in how well pupils do in school. However, some researchers have

discovered that professional development activities have little impact on the performance of the teachers, despite the fact that it has never been properly analyzed to meet the needs of the teachers. Professional development is also not related to the effectiveness of teaching strategy in the classroom and lacks passion and follow-up but this study suggests that strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation of professional development activities could benefit teachers more (Capuno; et al,2021). Teacher professional learning is of increasing interest as a critical way to support the increasingly complex skills students need to learn in order to succeed in the 21st century. Sophisticated forms of teaching are needed to develop student competencies such as deep mastery of challenging content, critical thinking, complex problem solving, effective communication and collaboration, and self-direction. In turn, effective professional development (PD) is needed to help teachers learn and refine the instructional strategies required to teach these skills (Hammond et al.,2017) Teacher trainers are among those who are engaged in the learning of learners, educators, and ongoing PD of in-service educators (Czerniawski et al., 2019).

Nonetheless, in the last 20 years, scholars, and teacher trainers themselves began to growingly notice the particular quality of their jobs, and so, they have begun to emphasize teacher trainers' PD (Berry, 2016; Lunenberg et al., 2017). Thus, an educational space is a location for students to gain new knowledge and abilities, as well as a place for educators to study and further their professions. And EFL instructors must acquire the most recent education knowledge and abilities within the context of English language education and learning in order to improve learners' development and growth while meeting global needs (Zhiyong et al., 2020). To fully comprehend and support educator trainers' professional development, it is critical to understand what skills and information they require and how they learn such skills and knowledge efficiently during their careers (MacPhail et al., 2019). Professional development programs boost job happiness by assisting in the creation of a satisfying work environment. setting in which educators can gain skills and resources to overcome issues in their profession (Spratt ,2019)).

Despite the fact that the intricacy of Faculty Development processes has been recognized in the introduction of comprehensive evaluation frameworks, numerous loopholes remain must be completed in order for faculty developers to conduct evaluations of this complexity must take into account and contribute to the development of an empirical knowledge base (Phuong, Cole, & Zarestky et al., 2018). According to Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), the purpose of any Professional development (PD) is used to improve teachers' knowledge and skills. When implementing a PD model, the major consideration is as Lesson Study (LS), is thus to see if it can cause these modifications (Guskey, 2021), who advocates for comprehensive PD assessments that produce replicable and comparative data, agrees identifying and defining key components that contribute to the effectiveness of PD, and ways in which they can be adapted can be a fruitful method to work. Darling-Hammond and colleagues (2017) underline the need of credible techniques of evaluating teachers on their PD work. If practitioners understand how to identify the conditions required, to improve their outcomes, such as more time, space, or expertise, this could help them communicate

these needs to school boards, policymakers or administrations (Darling-Hammond et al. 2017). In this regard, The Department of Education (DepEd) is devoted to providing Education of high quality. Aside from creating enhancements to physical facilities and DepEd is also attempting to improve the curriculum. Create effective teachers. A good instructor is always expected to develop a high-quality learner. Teachers' quality performance is equivalent to fantastic outcome for the achievement of the vision of the Department for the Filipino people. Gender and Development, In-service trainings and Learning Action Cell programs are some enhancement programs conducted by the Department of Education in every school through the initiative of the school heads and training and development coordinators. Those programs which are usually conducted during semestral breaks lead teachers to cope up with the difficulties and problems met in the previous grading periods. However, such development programs shall be done in consultation with relevant DepEd units and stakeholders, towards aim for professional development (DepEd Advisory No.147 s.2017).

Although such studies discussed teachers' views on professional development, it is unable to provide a more general description of school atmosphere, student achievement, or teachers' knowledge and skills. In order to provide professional development that is in line with teachers' perceptions of their needs and secures the participation of the teachers, it is crucial for schools and administrators to take- into account the diverse backgrounds of teachers and students, to provide numerous, interconnected opportunities for professional colleagues to interact with one another, and to work to create a school environment that maximizes opportunities for collaboration as well as for learning.

A teacher's dedication cannot be gauged by the number of years spent in the profession or the they have on their student's lives; rather, it must be determined by how much time and effort they are willing to devote to advancing and deepening the knowledge that must be imparted to students. The participation of teachers in ongoing professional development is crucial for advancing knowledge and abilities while quickly improving the teaching and learning process (Schleicher, 2017). With these, each teacher will understand why they are losing interest in furthering their education, especially in enrolling in master's and doctoral programs as teachers' engagement in professional development is impeded by several factors or reasons.

In fact, review of these researches revealed salient research gaps that need further investigation. Notably, studies that shall design and initiate programs for professional development of teachers based on their specific needs and the factors or barriers that may affect their engagement in these programs are needed (Eroglu & Kaya, 2021; Sahagun & Matriano,2019)). Interestingly, these investigations could use quantitative, qualitative, or mixed method approaches (Sahagun & Matriano, 2019). Such investigation will pave way to the strategic planning, implementation, and evaluation of professional development activities that could benefit teachers more (Padillo et al., 2021; Haq & Zulfgar, 2018). Hence, this study is being proposed.

A strong faculty development program that may increase the teacher's knowledge is essential to providing high-quality instruction and knowledge. It can provide a successful and reasonable method for carrying out best practices and achieving objectives. The professional viewpoint of the teacher can have a significant role in developing proficiency. The teacher's understanding of the subject matter and love for the job can pique pupils' interest and boost achievement and academic performance of students. Consequently, even when a teacher receives little advantage from the activities for professional growth. Professional development initiatives were found to have no impact on the teacher's professional development needs. Despite this, there has never been a thorough analysis of teachers' performance to meet their demands. At this time, Professional development lacks passion and is unrelated to the efficiency of teaching techniques in classrooms. Nevertheless, this study demonstrates that professional strategic planning, execution, and evaluation teacher development initiatives could be more advantageous. Therefore, this study proposes to design and initiate an input for a localized framework in the implementation of faculty development.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of perception of the teachers on their professional needs along:
 - a. Content Knowledge on Pedagogy
 - b. Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners
 - c. Curriculum in Planning
 - d. Assessment and Reporting
 - e. Community Linkages and Professional Engagement
 - f. Personal Growth and Professional Development
 - g. Plus Factor
2. What is the level of agreement of teachers on the factors that affect their professional development?
3. What are the strengths and weaknesses of teachers?
4. What localized framework in the implementation of the faculty development can be Developed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

"This study will employ a descriptive survey as its research design. A descriptive survey is a method of collecting data that provides an in-depth understanding of a population's characteristics. Given that this study aims to identify and describe the professional development needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District, Alilem, Ilocos Sur, using a questionnaire, the researcher found this design to be appropriate for the study."

Population and Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted at Alilem District, Alilem Ilocos Sur during the school year 2023-2024. The respondents of the study will be the elementary teachers of the said district. They will be chosen using total enumeration sampling. The total number of respondents is shown in table 1.

Age Group	Number of Respondents
25-30	5
31-40	5
41-50	9
51-60	10
61-64	1
TOTAL	30

Research Instrument

"In gathering pertinent data, the researcher will use a self-made questionnaire. Questionnaires are indeed popular tools used by researchers to collect data. They can be designed in various formats, such as multiple choice. The questionnaire will have two parts. The first part will assess the teachers' perception of their professional needs. The second part will gauge the teachers' level of agreement on the factors that affect their professional development and will identify the teachers' strengths and weaknesses. Notably, the research instrument will undergo validity and reliability testing before being used in the study."

Data Gathering Procedure

"To gather the necessary data, the researcher employed a qualitative approach, using questionnaires. This approach allowed the researcher to capture a broad range of responses through the survey. The participants in this study were elementary teachers from the Alilem District. They were chosen to participate based on their willingness and availability. In total, the researcher gathered data from 30 teachers, providing a rich and diverse set of perspectives. In the following sections, the researcher will detail the specific instruments used for data collection, the step-by-step procedure of the data gathering process, how the data was handled and stored, and the ethical considerations adhered to throughout the study."

Treatment of Data

In analyzing and interpreting the gathered data, the mean will be used to describe the level of perception of the teachers regarding their professional needs and the level of agreement among the teachers on the factors that affect their engagement in any of the initiated professional development activities. The mean will also be used to describe the level of validity of the faculty development program for teachers

Data Categorization

The norm below will be used in interpreting the data:

1	1.0 - 1.60	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)
2	1.61 - 2.20	Disagree (D),	Low(L)
3	2.21 - 3.40	Agree(A)	High (H)
4	3.41 - 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I: Level of perception of the teachers on their professional needs.

Table 1: Content Knowledge on Pedagogy

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars in improving my teaching strategies	3.60	SA
I need trainings and seminars particularly in terms of managing behavior and creating a positive learning environment.	3.67	SA
I need trainings and seminars in creating and grading assessments, as well as using assessment data	3.60	SA
I need trainings and seminars in developing and adapting curriculum to meet the needs of our students. This could include learning how to align lessons with standards, how to incorporate real-world examples into lessons, or how to create engaging and relevant lessons	3.77	SA
I need an opportunity to collaborate with other teachers, attend professional development workshops, or pursue further education	3.87	SA
I need trainings and seminars in improving my teaching strategies	3.60	SA
OVERALL	3.70	VH
MEAN		

Legend

Range of Ratings	Descriptive Rating (DR)	Overall DR
3:41 – 4:00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)

2:21 – 3:40	Agree (A)	High (H)
1:61 – 2:20	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
1:00 – 1:60	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low(VL)

Table 1, derived from a survey conducted among elementary teachers in Alilem District, presents the level of perception of teachers regarding their professional development needs, specifically focusing on content knowledge and pedagogy. The table provides a valuable input for a localized framework in the implementation of faculty development.

The table is organized with various professional development indicators listed in the rows and the corresponding mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) in the columns. The indicators represent different areas where the teachers feel they need training or seminars. The mean scores range from 1.00 to 4.00, with higher scores indicating stronger agreement with the need for professional development in the stated area. The descriptive ratings (DR) provide a qualitative interpretation of the mean scores, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

According to the table, all indicators have a mean score above 3.60, which corresponds to a "Strongly Agree" rating. This suggests that the teachers perceive a high need for professional development in all the stated areas. The highest mean score is 3.87 for the indicator "I need an opportunity to collaborate with other teachers, attend professional development workshops, or pursue further education".

These results indicate a strong perceived need for professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District, particularly in the areas of collaboration, attending professional development workshops, and further education. The teachers also expressed a strong need for training and seminars in improving teaching strategies, managing behavior, creating a positive learning environment, creating and grading assessments, and developing and adapting curriculum.

In conclusion, the table reveals a significant perceived need for professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District. This underscores the importance of incorporating a wide range of professional development opportunities, including collaboration, workshops, further education, and targeted trainings, into a localized framework for faculty development. The overall mean score of 3.70, which corresponds to a "Very High" rating, further emphasizes the perceived importance of these professional development needs.

Table 2: Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need seminars and trainings on understanding the diverse backgrounds and learning styles of the students. This could include training on cultural competency, understanding different learning disabilities, and strategies for teaching English language learners.	3.70	SA
I need seminars and trainings on how to create an inclusive classroom environment. This could include strategies for differentiating instruction, using inclusive language, and creating a classroom culture that values diversity.	3.68	SA
I need seminars and trainings on how to manage a diverse classroom effectively. This could include strategies for managing behavior, creating a positive learning environment, and dealing with conflicts.	3.60	SA
I need professional development on how to adapt curriculum to meet the needs of diverse learners. This could include training on how to modify lessons and assessments, how to incorporate multicultural perspectives into the curriculum, and how to use technology to support diverse learners.	3.20	A
I need seminars and trainings on how to collaborate effectively with other educators, parents, and community members to support diverse learners. This could include strategies for effective communication, team teaching, and community engagement.	3.53	SA
I need professional development on the legal and ethical considerations related to teaching diverse learners. This could include training on special education law, confidentiality, and ethical decision-making.	3.47	A
	3.53	VH
Overall Mean		

Table 2, derived from a survey conducted among elementary teachers in Alilem District, presents the level of perception of teachers regarding their professional development needs, specifically focusing on learning environment and diversity of learners. This data serves as a crucial input for a localized framework in the implementation of faculty development.

The table is organized with various professional development indicators listed in the rows and the corresponding mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) in the columns. The indicators represent different areas where the teachers feel they need seminars or trainings. The mean scores range from 1.00 to 4.00, with higher scores indicating stronger agreement with the need for professional development in the stated area. The descriptive

ratings (DR) provide a qualitative interpretation of the mean scores, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree".

According to the table, most indicators have a mean score above 3.50, which corresponds to a "Strongly Agree" rating. This suggests that the teachers perceive a high need for professional development in most of the stated areas. The highest mean score is 3.70 for the indicator "I need seminars and trainings on understanding the diverse backgrounds and learning styles of the students."

These results indicate a strong perceived need for professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District, particularly in the areas of understanding student diversity, creating an inclusive classroom environment, and managing a diverse classroom effectively. The teachers also expressed a need for professional development in adapting curriculum to meet the needs of diverse learners, collaborating effectively with other stakeholders, and understanding the legal and ethical considerations related to teaching diverse learners.

In conclusion, the table reveals a significant perceived need for professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District, particularly in relation to the learning environment and diversity of learners. The overall mean score of 3.53, which corresponds to a "Very High" rating, further emphasizes the perceived importance of these professional development needs.

Table 3: Curriculum Planning

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars on understanding and interpreting curriculum standards. This includes both national and local standards, as well as any specific standards for their subject area.	3.33	A
I need trainings and seminars on how to develop effective lesson plans. This could include training on how to align lessons with standards, how to structure a lesson, and how to incorporate a variety of teaching strategies.	3.43	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to differentiate instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners. This could include strategies for modifying lessons and assessments, as well as strategies for teaching students with different learning styles and abilities.	3.43	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to integrate technology into the curriculum. This could include training on how to use specific educational software, how to incorporate online resources into lessons, and how to use technology to enhance student learning.	3.57	SA

I need trainings and seminars on how to assess student learning effectively. This could include training on how to develop and grade assessments, how to use formative and summative assessments, and how to use assessment data to inform instruction.	3.60	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to make connections between the subject area and other subjects. This could include strategies for integrating literacy, math, science, and social studies into their curriculum.	3.57	A
Overall Mean	3.49	VH

Table 3 presents the results of a survey on the curriculum planning needs of educators. It highlights the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for various indicators related to professional development in curriculum planning.

"Understanding and interpreting curriculum standards": The mean score for this indicator is 3.33, which falls into the "Agree" category. This suggests that teachers perceive a need for trainings and seminars to understand and interpret both national and local curriculum standards.

"Developing effective lesson plans": The mean score for this indicator is 3.43, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. This signifies a high perceived need for trainings and seminars on developing lesson plans that align with standards, have a well-structured format, and incorporate diverse teaching strategies.

"Differentiating instruction for diverse learners": This indicator also has a mean score of 3.43, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for professional development in strategies for modifying lessons and assessments to meet the needs of diverse learners with different learning styles and abilities.

"Integrating technology into the curriculum": The mean score for this indicator is 3.57, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators recognize the importance of trainings and seminars on effectively incorporating technology, such as educational software and online resources, into their curriculum to enhance student learning. "Assessing student learning effectively": This indicator has a mean score of 3.60, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers express a high need for professional development in developing and grading assessments, utilizing formative and summative assessments, and using assessment data to inform instruction.

"Making connections between subject areas": The mean score for this indicator is 3.57, which corresponds to an "Agree" rating. Educators indicate a need for trainings and seminars on integrating literacy, math, science, and social studies into their curriculum, fostering interdisciplinary connections.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.49 reflects a "Very High" rating, indicating a significant perceived need for professional development in curriculum planning among

educators. These findings emphasize the importance of providing targeted training and support to enhance educators' skills in understanding standards, developing effective lesson plans, differentiating instruction, integrating technology, assessing student learning, and making interdisciplinary connections.

Based on the mean score of 3.49 in Table 3, there is a high perceived need for professional development in curriculum planning among educators. The overall mean score falls into the "Very High" rating category, indicating that teachers strongly agree on the need for trainings and seminars in various aspects of curriculum planning. This suggests that educators recognize the importance of enhancing their skills and knowledge in areas such as understanding curriculum standards, developing effective lesson plans, differentiating instruction, integrating technology, assessing student learning, and making interdisciplinary connections. The high mean score reflects a significant perceived need for professional development in curriculum planning among educators.

Table 4: Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars on different types of assessments, such as formative, summative, and diagnostic assessments. This includes understanding the purpose of each assessment type and how to use them effectively.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to develop valid and reliable assessments that align with learning objectives and standards. This could include training on creating rubrics, designing multiple-choice questions, and developing performance-based assessments.	3.33	A
I need trainings and seminars in analyzing and interpreting assessment data to inform their instruction. This could include training on how to use data to identify student strengths and weaknesses, adjust teaching strategies, and provide targeted interventions.	3.43	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to provide constructive feedback to students that helps them understand their progress and areas for improvement. This could include training on using specific, actionable language and providing feedback that promotes growth mindset.	3.43	SA
I need trainings and seminars in implementing effective assessment strategies in their classrooms. This could include training on creating a balanced assessment plan, using technology for assessments, and incorporating authentic assessments.	3.53	SA
	3.47	SA

I need trainings and seminars on how to effectively communicate student progress to parents or guardians. This could include training on writing clear and informative progress reports, conducting parent-teacher conferences, and maintaining open lines of communication.

3.44 VH

Overall Mean

Table 4 presents the results of a survey on the assessment and reporting needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It highlights the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for various indicators related to professional development in assessment and reporting.

"Different types of assessments": The mean score for this indicator is 3.47, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers perceive a high need for trainings and seminars on understanding and effectively using different types of assessments, such as formative, summative, and diagnostic assessments.

"Developing valid and reliable assessments": The mean score for this indicator is 3.33, falling into the "Agree" category. Teachers express a need for professional development in developing assessments that align with learning objectives and standards, including the creation of rubrics, designing multiple-choice questions, and developing performance-based assessments.

"Analyzing and interpreting assessment data": This indicator has a mean score of 3.43, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators recognize the importance of trainings and seminars on using assessment data to inform their instruction, identify student strengths and weaknesses, adjust teaching strategies, and provide targeted interventions.

"Providing constructive feedback to students": The mean score for this indicator is 3.43, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for professional development in providing feedback that helps students understand their progress and areas for improvement, including using specific, actionable language and promoting a growth mindset.

"Implementing effective assessment strategies": This indicator has a mean score of 3.53, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers perceive a high need for trainings and seminars on implementing effective assessment strategies in their classrooms, including creating a balanced assessment plan, using technology for assessments, and incorporating authentic assessments.

"Effectively communicating student progress to parents": The mean score for this indicator is 3.47, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators express a need for professional development in effectively communicating student progress to parents or guardians, including writing clear and informative progress reports, conducting parent-teacher conferences, and maintaining open lines of communication.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.44 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant perceived need for professional development in assessment and reporting among elementary teachers in Alilem District. These findings emphasize the importance of providing targeted training and support to enhance educators' skills in various aspects of assessment, data analysis, feedback provision, and effective communication with parents or guardians.

Table 5: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars on how to establish and maintain partnerships with community organizations, businesses, and local resources. This could include strategies for reaching out, building relationships, and collaborating on projects or initiatives.	3.57	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to effectively engage parents and families in our students' education. This could include training on effective communication strategies, involving parents in decision-making processes, and fostering a positive home-school relationship.	3.73	SA
I need trainings and seminars in developing effective collaboration skills with our colleagues. This could include training on team teaching, co-planning lessons, and sharing best practices. PD opportunities that promote a collaborative culture and encourage peer learning can be particularly beneficial.	3.57	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to actively participate in and contribute to professional learning communities (PLCs). This could include training on effective PLC structures, protocols for collaboration, and using PLCs as a platform for sharing ideas and resources.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars on how to build and maintain professional networks. This could include training on attending conferences, joining professional organizations, and utilizing online platforms for professional networking.	3.40	A
I need trainings and seminars in pursuing continuing education and engaging in lifelong learning. This could include training on accessing professional development opportunities, exploring advanced coursework, and staying updated on current research and trends in education.	3.63	SA
	3.56	VH
Overall Mean		

Table 5 focuses on the community linkages and professional engagement needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for various indicators related to professional development in this area.

"Establishing and maintaining partnerships with community organizations": The mean score for this indicator is 3.57, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for trainings and seminars on strategies for reaching out, building relationships, and collaborating with community organizations, businesses, and local resources.

"Effectively engaging parents and families": This indicator has a mean score of 3.73, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Educators recognize the importance of professional development in effective communication strategies, involving parents in decision-making processes, and fostering a positive home-school relationship.

"Developing collaboration skills with colleagues": The mean score for this indicator is 3.57, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a need for professional development opportunities that promote collaboration, such as team teaching, co-planning lessons, and sharing best practices.

"Participating in professional learning communities (PLCs)": This indicator has a mean score of 3.47, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators express a need for trainings and seminars on effective PLC structures, collaboration protocols, and using PLCs as platforms for sharing ideas and resources.

"Building and maintaining professional networks": The mean score for this indicator is 3.40, falling into the "Agree" category. Teachers express a need for professional development in building and maintaining professional networks, including attending conferences, joining professional organizations, and utilizing online platforms for networking.

"Pursuing continuing education and lifelong learning": This indicator has a mean score of 3.63, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators express a strong need for trainings and seminars on accessing professional development opportunities, exploring advanced coursework, and staying updated on current research and trends in education.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.56 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant perceived need for professional development in community linkages and professional engagement among elementary teachers in Alilem District. These findings emphasize the importance of providing targeted training and support to enhance educators' skills in establishing community partnerships, engaging parents and families, fostering collaboration, participating in professional learning communities, building professional networks, and pursuing lifelong learning.

Table 6: Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars on self-reflection techniques, journaling, and peer observation to critically analyze the teaching methods, strategies, and interactions with students	3.67	SA
I need trainings and seminars in expanding repertoire of instructional strategies to engage students and promote active learning. This could include PD on incorporating project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, or technology-enhanced instruction.	3.33	A
I need trainings and seminars on how to effectively differentiate instruction to meet the diverse needs of the students. This could include strategies for adapting lessons, providing accommodations, and modifying assessments.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars that focuses on classroom management techniques and behavior support strategies. This could include training on establishing clear expectations, implementing positive behavior interventions, and fostering a positive classroom culture.	3.33	A
I need trainings and seminars on how to effectively integrate technology into the teaching practice. This could include training on using educational apps, online resources, and digital tools to enhance instruction and student engagement.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars that enhances the cultural competence and equips them with strategies to create an inclusive and equitable classroom environment. This could include training on culturally responsive teaching, addressing bias, and promoting social justice in the classroom.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars in developing leadership skills and pursuing opportunities for professional growth. This could include PD on mentorship, instructional coaching, and pathways for career advancement.	3.70	SA
Overall Mean	3.50	VH

Table 6 focuses on the personal growth and professional development needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for various indicators related to professional development in this area.

"Self-reflection techniques, journaling, and peer observation": The mean score for this indicator is 3.67, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for trainings and seminars on self-reflection techniques, journaling, and peer observation to critically analyse their teaching methods, strategies, and interactions with students.

"Expanding repertoire of instructional strategies": This indicator has a mean score of 3.33, falling into the "Agree" category. Educators express a need for professional development in expanding their repertoire of instructional strategies to engage students and promote active learning. This could include training on project-based learning, inquiry-based learning, or technology-enhanced instruction.

"Effectively differentiating instruction": The mean score for this indicator is 3.47, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a need for trainings and seminars on effectively differentiating instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students. This includes strategies for adapting lessons, providing accommodations, and modifying assessments.

"Classroom management techniques and behaviour support strategies": This indicator also has a mean score of 3.33, indicating an "Agree" rating. Educators express a need for professional development in classroom management techniques and behaviour support strategies. This could include training on establishing clear expectations, implementing positive behaviour interventions, and fostering a positive classroom culture.

"Effectively integrating technology": The mean score for this indicator is 3.47, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers express a need for trainings and seminars on effectively integrating technology into their teaching practice. This includes training on using educational apps, online resources, and digital tools to enhance instruction and student engagement.

"Enhancing cultural competence and creating an inclusive and equitable classroom environment": This indicator has a mean score of 3.47, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators express a need for professional development in enhancing their cultural competence and equipping themselves with strategies to create an inclusive and equitable classroom environment. This could include training on culturally responsive teaching, addressing bias, and promoting social justice in the classroom.

"Developing leadership skills and pursuing professional growth": The mean score for this indicator is 3.70, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for trainings and seminars in developing leadership skills and pursuing opportunities for professional growth. This could include professional development on mentorship, instructional coaching, and pathways for career advancement.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.50 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant perceived need for personal growth and professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District. These findings emphasize

the importance of providing targeted training and support to enhance educators' skills in self-reflection, instructional strategies, differentiation, classroom management, technology integration, cultural competence, and leadership development.

Table 7: Plus Factor

Indicators	MEAN	DR
I need trainings and seminars on how to develop well-structured and engaging lesson plans. This could include training on aligning objectives, incorporating different instructional strategies, and utilizing appropriate resources.	3.67	SA
I need trainings and seminars on classroom management strategies that help in creating a positive and productive learning environment. This could include training on establishing routines, managing transitions, and addressing student behavior effectively.	3.63	SA
I need trainings and seminars in implementing differentiated instruction to meet the diverse needs of the students. PD in this area could focus on strategies for adapting content, process, and products to accommodate various learning styles and abilities.	3.70	SA
I need trainings and seminars on effective questioning techniques can help teachers engage students in critical thinking and promote deeper understanding. This could include training on asking open-ended questions, using probing techniques, and facilitating meaningful discussions.	3.57	SA
I need trainings and seminars on designing and implementing formative and summative assessments. This could include training on creating rubrics, providing constructive feedback, and using assessment data to inform instruction.	3.47	SA
I need trainings and seminars on integrating technology into teaching practices can help teachers leverage digital tools and resources to enhance instruction and student engagement. This could include training on using educational apps, online platforms, and multimedia resources effectively.	3.40	A
I need trainings and seminars on collaborative learning strategies that can support teachers in promoting teamwork, communication, and problem-solving skills among students. This could include training on cooperative learning structures, group work facilitation, and fostering a collaborative classroom culture.	3.63	SA
	3.54	VH
Overall Mean		

Table 7 focuses on the plus factors, or additional areas of professional development needs, of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for various indicators related to professional development in these areas.

"Developing well-structured and engaging lesson plans": The mean score for this indicator is 3.67, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for trainings and seminars on developing lesson plans that are well-structured and engaging, including aligning objectives, incorporating different instructional strategies, and utilizing appropriate resources.

"Classroom management strategies": This indicator has a mean score of 3.63, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Educators express a need for professional development in classroom management strategies that help create a positive and productive learning environment. This could include training on establishing routines, managing transitions, and addressing student behavior effectively.

"Implementing differentiated instruction": The mean score for this indicator is 3.70, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a strong need for professional development in implementing differentiated instruction to meet the diverse needs of their students. This could focus on strategies for adapting content, process, and products to accommodate various learning styles and abilities.

"Effective questioning techniques": This indicator has a mean score of 3.57, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Educators express a need for trainings and seminars on effective questioning techniques that can engage students in critical thinking and promote deeper understanding. This could include training on asking open-ended questions, using probing techniques, and facilitating meaningful discussions.

"Designing and implementing assessments": The mean score for this indicator is 3.47, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers express a need for professional development in designing and implementing formative and summative assessments. This could include training on creating rubrics, providing constructive feedback, and using assessment data to inform instruction.

"Integrating technology into teaching practices": This indicator has a mean score of 3.40, indicating an "Agree" rating. Educators express a need for trainings and seminars on integrating technology into their teaching practices to enhance instruction and student engagement. This could include training on using educational apps, online platforms, and multimedia resources effectively.

"Collaborative learning strategies": The mean score for this indicator is 3.63, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers express a need for professional development in collaborative learning strategies that support promoting teamwork, communication, and problem-solving skills among students. This could include training

on cooperative learning structures, group work facilitation, and fostering a collaborative classroom culture.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.54 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant perceived need for professional development in these plus factors among elementary teachers in Alilem District. These findings highlight the importance of providing targeted training and support to enhance educators' skills in lesson planning, classroom management, differentiated instruction, questioning techniques, assessment design, technology integration, and collaborative learning strategies.

SUMMARY TABLE

PART I: What is the level of perception of the teachers on their professional needs along:

TABLE		MEAN	DR
1	Content Knowledge on Pedagogy	3.70	VH
2	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	3.53	VH
3	Curriculum Planning	3.49	VH
4	Assessment and Reporting	3.44	VH
5	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.56	VH
6	Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.50	VH
7	Plus Factor	3.54	VH
Overall Mean		3.54	VH

The summary table provides an overview of the level of perception among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding their professional development needs in different areas. The table includes the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for each category.

Content Knowledge on Pedagogy: The mean score is 3.70, indicating a "Very High" rating. Teachers perceive a strong need for professional development in enhancing their content knowledge and pedagogical skills.

Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners: The mean score is 3.53, falling into the "Very High" category. Educators express a significant need for professional development in creating inclusive and supportive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students.

Curriculum Planning: The mean score is 3.49, reflecting a "Very High" rating. Teachers recognize the importance of professional development in curriculum planning, including understanding curriculum standards and developing effective lesson plans.

Assessment and Reporting: The mean score is 3.44, indicating a "Very High" rating. Educators perceive a high need for professional development in various aspects of assessment and reporting, such as understanding different assessment types and analyzing assessment data.

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement: The mean score is 3.56, falling into the "Very High" category. Teachers express a significant need for professional development in establishing partnerships with community organizations, engaging parents, and collaborating with colleagues.

Personal Growth and Professional Development: The mean score is 3.50, reflecting a "Very High" rating. Educators recognize the importance of personal growth and ongoing professional development in areas such as self-reflection, instructional strategies, and leadership skills.

Plus- Factor: The mean score is 3.54, indicating a "Very High" rating. Teachers express a strong need for professional development in additional areas such as lesson planning, classroom management, differentiated instruction, and technology integration. Overall, the table's mean score of 3.54 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant perceived need for professional development among elementary teachers in Alilem District across various areas. These findings highlight the importance of providing targeted and comprehensive faculty development programs that address the identified professional needs of the teachers.

Based on the summary table, the areas of professional development that elementary teachers in Alilem District perceive as their highest priority are: Content Knowledge on Pedagogy: This category received the highest mean score of 3.70, indicating a "Very High" rating. Teachers prioritize enhancing their content knowledge and pedagogical skills to effectively deliver instruction to their students. Personal Growth and Professional Development: This category received a mean score of 3.50, also falling into the "Very High" rating. Teachers prioritize their personal growth and ongoing professional development in areas such as self-reflection, instructional strategies, and leadership skills. Plus- Factor: This category received a mean score of 3.54, reflecting a "Very High" rating. Teachers prioritize additional areas of professional development, such as lesson planning, classroom management, differentiated instruction, effective questioning techniques, assessment design, technology integration, and collaborative learning strategies.

While all categories in the summary table indicate a high level of perceived need for professional development, the areas of content knowledge on pedagogy, personal growth and professional development, and the plus factor seem to be the highest priorities for elementary teachers in Alilem District. These areas reflect the teachers' desire to enhance their teaching skills, create a positive learning environment, and continuously improve their practice to meet the diverse needs of their students.

Part II: Level of agreement of teachers on the factors that affect their professional development

Table 1: Personal Factor

Indicators	MEAN	DR
Teachers' personal teaching philosophies and beliefs about education can influence their PD needs. For example, a teacher who values student-centered learning may seek PD opportunities that focus on inquiry-based teaching methods or student engagement strategies.	3.87	SA
Teachers' career aspirations and professional goals can drive their PD needs. Some teachers may aspire to take on leadership roles, such as becoming a department head or instructional coach, and may require PD in areas like instructional leadership, mentoring, or curriculum development.	3.90	SA
Teachers' personal interests and passions can shape their PD needs. They may seek opportunities to deepen their knowledge and skills in specific subject areas, instructional methods, or educational approaches that align with their interests and passions.	3.87	SA
Teachers' self-assessment of their strengths and areas for growth can influence their PD needs. They may seek PD opportunities that build on their strengths or address specific areas where they feel they need improvement.	3.90	SA
Teachers' preferred learning styles and preferences can impact their PD needs. Some teachers may prefer hands-on workshops or collaborative learning experiences, while others may prefer self-paced online courses or reading professional literature.	3.87	SA
Teachers' personal circumstances, such as family responsibilities or other commitments, can impact their PD needs. They may require flexible PD options that accommodate their work-life balance and time constraints.	3.90	SA
Teachers' motivation and commitment to continuous learning can influence their PD needs. Some teachers may be highly motivated to seek out PD opportunities and take initiative in their professional growth, while others may require additional support or encouragement.	3.87	SA
Overall mean	3.88	VH

Table 1 focuses on the personal factors that can influence the professional development (PD) needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for each indicator.

Teachers' personal teaching philosophies and beliefs: The mean score for this indicator is 3.87, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' personal teaching philosophies and beliefs about education can influence their PD needs. For example, teachers who value student-centered learning may seek PD opportunities that focus on inquiry-based teaching methods or student engagement strategies.

Teachers' career aspirations and professional goals: This indicator has a mean score of 3.90, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers' career aspirations and professional goals can drive their PD needs. Some teachers may aspire to take on leadership roles, such as becoming a department head or instructional coach, and may require PD in areas like instructional leadership, mentoring, or curriculum development.

Teachers' personal interests and passions: The mean score for this indicator is 3.87, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' personal interests and passions can shape their PD needs. They may seek opportunities to deepen their knowledge and skills in specific subject areas, instructional methods, or educational approaches that align with their interests and passions.

Teachers' self-assessment of strengths and areas for growth: This indicator also has a mean score of 3.90, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' self-assessment of their strengths and areas for growth can influence their PD needs. They may seek PD opportunities that build on their strengths or address specific areas where they feel they need improvement.

Teachers' preferred learning styles and preferences: The mean score for this indicator is 3.87, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers' preferred learning styles and preferences can impact their PD needs. Some teachers may prefer hands-on workshops or collaborative learning experiences, while others may prefer self-paced online courses or reading professional literature.

Teachers' personal circumstances: The mean score for this indicator is 3.90, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' personal circumstances, such as family responsibilities or other commitments, can impact their PD needs. They may require flexible PD options that accommodate their work-life balance and time constraints.

Teachers' motivation and commitment to continuous learning: The mean score for this indicator is 3.87, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' motivation and commitment to continuous learning can influence their PD needs. Some teachers may be highly motivated to seek out PD opportunities and take initiative in their professional growth, while others may require additional support or encouragement.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.88 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant level of agreement among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding the personal factors that can influence their PD needs. These findings highlight the importance of considering teachers' personal beliefs, goals, interests, self-assessment, learning styles, circumstances, motivation, and commitment when designing and implementing faculty development programs. Providing personalized and tailored PD

opportunities that align with these personal factors can enhance teachers' engagement and effectiveness in their professional growth.

Table 2: Financial Factor

Indicators	MEAN	DR
Teachers may consider the cost associated with PD opportunities when determining their needs. Some PD programs or workshops may require registration fees, travel expenses, or materials costs. Teachers with limited financial resources may need to prioritize or seek out more affordable options.	3.93	SA
The availability of funding or financial support for PD can significantly impact teachers' ability to pursue their desired professional development. Teachers may seek out grants, scholarships, or district-sponsored funding opportunities to support their PD needs.	3.90	SA
Financial constraints can affect teachers' access to PD resources. Teachers in low-income schools or districts with limited budgets may have fewer opportunities for PD, such as attending conferences, purchasing instructional materials, or accessing online courses.	3.90	SA
Financial incentives or compensation for participating in PD can influence teachers' motivation to engage in professional development. Offering stipends, salary increases, or reimbursements for PD-related expenses can encourage teachers to invest in their professional growth.	3.93	SA
Financial considerations can also play a role in teachers' PD needs when it comes to career advancement. Teachers seeking promotions or higher-paying positions may prioritize PD opportunities that align with their career goals and offer potential financial benefits.	3.90	SA
Teachers' personal financial situations can impact their ability to allocate resources towards PD. Financial obligations, such as student loans, mortgages, or supporting dependents, may limit the amount of money teachers can invest in PD opportunities	3.90	SA
Overall Mean	3.92	VH

Table 2 focuses on the financial factors that can impact the professional development (PD) needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for each indicator.

Cost associated with PD opportunities: The mean score for this indicator is 3.93, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers consider the cost associated with PD opportunities when determining their needs. Some PD programs or workshops may require registration fees, travel expenses, or materials costs. Teachers with limited financial resources may need to prioritize or seek out more affordable options. Availability of funding or financial support for PD: This indicator has a mean score of 3.90, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers acknowledge that the availability of funding or financial support for PD can significantly impact their ability to pursue their desired professional development. They may seek out grants, scholarships, or district-sponsored funding opportunities to support their PD needs.

Financial constraints and access to PD resources: The mean score for this indicator is 3.90, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Financial constraints can affect teachers' access to PD resources, particularly for those in low-income schools or districts with limited budgets. They may have fewer opportunities for PD, such as attending conferences, purchasing instructional materials, or accessing online courses.

Financial incentives or compensation for participating in PD: This indicator also has a mean score of 3.93, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers recognize that financial incentives or compensation for participating in PD can influence their motivation to engage in professional development. Offering stipends, salary increases, or reimbursements for PD-related expenses can encourage teachers to invest in their professional growth.

Financial considerations and career advancement: The mean score for this indicator is 3.90, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Financial considerations can play a role in teachers' PD needs when it comes to career advancement. Teachers seeking promotions or higher-paying positions may prioritize PD opportunities that align with their career goals and offer potential financial benefits.

Personal financial situations and allocation of resources: The mean score for this indicator is 3.90, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers' personal financial situations can impact their ability to allocate resources towards PD. Financial obligations, such as student loans, mortgages, or supporting dependents, may limit the amount of money teachers can invest in PD opportunities.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.92 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant level of agreement among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding the financial factors that can impact their PD needs. These findings highlight the importance of considering the financial implications and providing support in terms of funding, grants, incentives, and affordable options when designing and implementing faculty development programs. Ensuring equitable access to PD resources is crucial to support teachers' professional growth and advancement.

Table 3: School-Related

Indicators	MEAN	DR
The school's culture and vision can shape teachers' PD needs. A school that values innovation and student-centered learning may require PD opportunities that align with these priorities, such as training on project-based learning or technology integration.	3.97	SA
The support and encouragement provided by school leaders can impact teachers' PD needs. When school leaders prioritize and invest in teacher development, it can create a culture of continuous learning and support teachers' desire for PD in various areas	4.00	SA
School-wide curriculum or instructional initiatives can influence teachers' PD needs. For example, if a school adopts a new instructional approach, such as blended learning or competency-based education, teachers may require PD to effectively implement these strategies.	3.97	SA
The availability of resources, both financial and material, can impact teachers' PD needs. Schools that provide funding for PD opportunities, access to instructional materials, and technology resources can better support teachers' professional growth.	3.97	SA
Collaborative opportunities within the school community can shape teachers' PD needs. Professional learning communities, grade-level or subject-area teams, and collaborative planning time can support teachers in sharing best practices, learning from one another, and identifying areas for professional growth.	4.00	SA
The school's approach to data and assessment can impact teachers' PD needs. If a school emphasizes data-driven instruction or formative assessment practices, teachers may require PD on data analysis, using assessment data to inform instruction, or designing effective assessments.	3.93	SA
The school's PD policies and support mechanisms can influence teachers' PD needs. Schools that provide dedicated PD time, mentorship programs, or opportunities for peer observation and feedback can better address teachers' individual needs and promote their professional growth.	3.97	SA
The characteristics and needs of the student population can impact teachers' PD needs. Schools with diverse student populations, including English language learners, students with special needs, or gifted students, may require PD opportunities that focus on meeting the unique needs of these students.	3.97	SA

Table 3 focuses on the school-related factors that can influence the professional development (PD) needs of elementary teachers in Alilem District. It presents the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for each indicator.

School's culture and vision: The mean score for this indicator is 3.97, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. The school's culture and vision can shape teachers' PD needs. A school that values innovation and student-centered learning may require PD opportunities that align with these priorities, such as training on project-based learning or technology integration.

Support and encouragement from school leaders: This indicator has a mean score of 4.00, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. The support and encouragement provided by school leaders can significantly impact teachers' PD needs. When school leaders prioritize and invest in teacher development, it creates a culture of continuous learning and supports teachers' desire for PD in various areas.

School-wide curriculum or instructional initiatives: The mean score for this indicator is 3.97, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. School-wide curriculum or instructional initiatives can influence teachers' PD needs. For example, if a school adopts a new instructional approach, such as blended learning or competency-based education, teachers may require PD to effectively implement these strategies.

Availability of resources: The mean score for this indicator is 3.97, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. The availability of resources, both financial and material, can impact teachers' PD needs. Schools that provide funding for PD opportunities, access to instructional materials, and technology resources can better support teachers' professional growth.

Collaborative opportunities within the school community: This indicator has a mean score of 4.00, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Collaborative opportunities within the school community, such as professional learning communities, grade-level or subject-area teams, and collaborative planning time, can shape teachers' PD needs. These opportunities support teachers in sharing best practices, learning from one another, and identifying areas for professional growth.

School's approach to data and assessment: The mean score for this indicator is 3.93, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. The school's approach to data and assessment can impact teachers' PD needs. If a school emphasizes data-driven instruction or formative assessment practices, teachers may require PD on data analysis, using assessment data to inform instruction, or designing effective assessments.

School's PD policies and support mechanisms: The mean score for this indicator is 3.97, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. The school's PD policies and support

mechanisms can influence teachers' PD needs. Schools that provide dedicated PD time, mentorship programs, or opportunities for peer observation and feedback can better address teachers' individual needs and promote their professional growth. Characteristics and needs of the student population: The mean score for this indicator is 3.97, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. The characteristics and needs of the student population can impact teachers' PD needs. Schools with diverse student populations, including English language learners, students with special needs, or gifted students, may require PD opportunities that focus on meeting the unique needs of these students.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.95 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant level of agreement among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding the school-related factors that can influence their PD needs. These findings highlight the importance of creating a supportive school culture, providing resources and collaborative opportunities, aligning PD with school initiatives, and implementing effective PD policies to address teachers' professional development needs.

SUMMARY TABLE:

Part II: What is the level of agreement of teachers on the factors that affect their professional development?

Table		MEAN	DR
1	Personal Factor	3.88	SA
2	Financial Factor	3.92	SA
3	School- Related	3.95	SA
Overall Mean		3.92	VH

The summary table provides an overview of the level of agreement among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding the factors that affect their professional development (PD). The table includes the mean scores and descriptive ratings (DR) for each factor.

Personal Factor: The mean score for this factor is 3.88, indicating a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers show a high level of agreement on the personal factors that influence their PD needs, such as their teaching philosophies, career aspirations, personal interests, self-assessment, preferred learning styles, personal circumstances, and motivation for continuous learning.

Financial Factor: The mean score for this factor is 3.92, falling into the "Strongly Agree" category. Teachers demonstrate a strong level of agreement on the financial factors that impact their PD opportunities, including the cost of PD, availability of funding or financial support, financial constraints, financial incentives, and personal financial situations.

School-Related Factor: The mean score for this factor is 3.95, reflecting a "Strongly Agree" rating. Teachers exhibit a high level of agreement on the school-related factors that affect their PD needs, such as the school's culture and vision, support from school leaders, school-wide curriculum or instructional initiatives, availability of resources, collaborative opportunities, approach to data and assessment, PD policies and support mechanisms, and characteristics and needs of the student population.

Overall, the table's mean score of 3.92 falls into the "Very High" rating category. This indicates a significant level of agreement among elementary teachers in Alilem District regarding the factors that influence their professional development. These findings highlight the importance of considering personal, financial, and school-related factors when designing and implementing a localized framework for faculty development. By addressing these factors, education stakeholders can better meet the PD needs of teachers and support their continuous growth and improvement.

Conclusions

PART I: What is the level of perception of the teachers on their professional needs along:

TABLE		MEAN	DR
1	Content Knowledge on Pedagogy	3.70	VH
2	Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	3.53	VH
3	Curriculum Planning	3.49	VH
4	Assessment and Reporting	3.44	VH
5	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.56	VH
6	Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.50	VH
7	Plus- Factor	3.54	VH
	Overall Mean	3.54	VH

Part II: What is the level of agreement of teachers on the factors that affect their professional development?

Table		MEAN	DR
1	Personal Factor	3.88	SA
2	Financial Factor	3.92	SA
3	School- Related	3.95	SA
	Overall Mean	3.92	VH

The two tables provide insights into the level of perception and agreement among teachers in Alilem District regarding their professional development needs. Table 1 highlights the level of perception among teachers on their professional needs in various areas. The mean scores and descriptive ratings indicate a "Very High" level of perception in each area, including content knowledge on pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages

and professional engagement, personal growth and professional development, and the plus factor. This suggests that teachers in Alilem District have a strong awareness of their professional development needs in these domains.

Table 2 focuses on the level of agreement among teachers regarding the factors that affect their professional development. The mean scores and descriptive ratings indicate a "Strongly Agree" level of agreement across the three factors: personal factor, financial factor, and school-related factor. This suggests that teachers in Alilem District are in agree about the influence of personal, financial, and school-related factors on their professional development needs.

Overall, these tables indicate that teachers in Alilem District have a strong perception of their professional development needs and are in agree about the factors that impact their development. This suggests a collective understanding and alignment among teachers regarding their strengths and weaknesses in professional development. The "Very High" level of perception and agreement highlight the potential for designing and implementing a localized framework for faculty development that addresses the identified needs and leverages the agreed-upon factors.

By capitalizing on the strengths identified in Table 1, such as content knowledge, learning environment, curriculum planning, assessment, community engagement, personal growth, and the plus factor, the district can build on these areas of expertise and provide targeted support and resources to further enhance teachers' professional development. Additionally, the agreement on the personal, financial, and school-related factors in Table 2 indicates the need to consider these factors in the design and implementation of faculty development initiatives. This can involve providing financial support, creating a supportive school culture, and fostering collaborative opportunities to address the identified needs.

Overall, these tables provide valuable insights for developing a localized framework for faculty development in Alilem District. By leveraging the strengths and addressing the identified needs, the district can create a tailored and effective professional development program that meets the specific requirements of teachers and ultimately improves their teaching practices and student outcomes.

A possible localized framework for faculty development in Alilem District can include the following components: Needs Assessment: Conduct a thorough needs assessment to identify the specific professional development needs of teachers in Alilem District. This can involve surveys, focus groups, and interviews to gather input from teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders. The needs assessment should consider the perceived needs highlighted in the previous tables, as well as any additional areas of focus that emerge.

Goal Setting: Based on the needs- assessment, establish clear and measurable goals for faculty development in Alilem District. These goals should align with the identified needs and the overall vision and mission of the district. Setting specific goals

will provide a framework for designing and evaluating the effectiveness of professional development initiatives.

Targeted Professional Development Programs: Develop targeted professional development programs that address the identified needs of teachers. These programs should be designed to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills in areas such as content knowledge on pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, personal growth and professional development, and the plus factor. The programs can include workshops, seminars, online courses, and coaching or mentoring opportunities.

Differentiated Support: Recognize that teachers have diverse needs and provide differentiated support based on their individual requirements. This can involve offering a variety of professional development opportunities that cater to different learning styles, experience levels, and subject areas. By providing differentiated support, the district can ensure that all teachers receive the necessary resources and guidance to meet their specific professional development needs.

Collaborative Learning Communities: Foster collaborative learning communities where teachers can engage in peer-to-peer learning and share best practices. This can be achieved through the establishment of professional learning communities (PLCs), grade-level or subject-area teams, and regular opportunities for collaboration and reflection. Collaborative learning communities provide a platform for teachers to learn from one another, exchange ideas, and collectively improve their teaching practices.

Mentoring and Coaching: Implement mentoring and coaching programs to support the professional growth of teachers. Experienced teachers can serve as mentors or coaches to provide guidance, feedback, and support to their colleagues. Mentoring and coaching relationships can help teachers refine their teaching practices, navigate challenges, and develop new skills.

Ongoing Support and Resources: Ensure that teachers have access to ongoing support and resources to facilitate their professional development. This can include providing instructional materials, technology tools, research-based resources, and opportunities for continued learning. Ongoing support and resources will enable teachers to stay updated with current pedagogical approaches and enhance their teaching practices.

Evaluation and Reflection: Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of the faculty development initiatives and encourage teachers to engage in reflection on their professional growth. This can involve collecting feedback from teachers, conducting self-assessments, and using data to inform future professional development efforts. Evaluation and reflection will help identify areas of success and areas for improvement within the faculty development framework.

By implementing a localized framework that incorporates these components, Alilem District can provide targeted and effective support for teachers' professional development. This framework will empower teachers to enhance their teaching practices, improve student learning outcomes, and contribute to the overall quality of education in the district.

Professional development for teachers is widely recognized as an essential component of a comprehensive system of teaching and learning. Here are some materials that corroborate the importance of professional development for teachers:

According to Hammond and Hylar (2017), well-designed and implemented professional development should be considered an essential component of a comprehensive system of teaching and learning. It supports students in developing the knowledge, skills, and competencies they need to thrive in the 21st century. Professional learning should be linked to teachers' experiences in preparation and induction, teaching standards, and evaluation. It should also bridge to leadership opportunities, ensuring a comprehensive system focused on the growth and development of teachers.

Worth and Van den Brande (2020) found that teachers express higher job satisfaction when they have autonomy over their own professional development. Allowing teachers to have a say in their learning and providing opportunities for personalized and self-directed professional development can contribute to their overall satisfaction and growth as educators.

These materials highlight the importance of professional development for teachers in enhancing their teaching practices, adapting to changing student needs, and fostering job satisfaction. By investing in effective professional development programs, districts can support the continuous growth and development of their teachers, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the insights provided by the tables and the importance of professional development for teachers, the following recommendations can be constructed;

1. Conduct a thorough needs assessment: Start by conducting a comprehensive needs assessment to identify the specific professional development needs of teachers in Alilem District. This can be done through surveys, focus groups, and interviews involving teachers, administrators, and other stakeholders. The needs assessment should consider the perceived needs highlighted in the tables and any additional areas of focus that emerge.

2. Establish clear and measurable goals: Based on the needs assessment, establish clear and measurable goals for faculty development in Alilem District. These

goals should align with the identified needs and the overall vision and mission of the district. Setting specific goals will provide a framework for designing and evaluating the effectiveness of professional development initiatives.

3. Develop targeted professional development programs: Design targeted professional development programs that address the identified needs of teachers. These programs should focus on enhancing teachers' knowledge and skills in areas such as content knowledge on pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, personal growth and professional development, and the plus factor. The programs can include workshops, seminars, online courses, and coaching or mentoring opportunities

4. Provide differentiated support: Recognize that teachers have diverse needs and provide differentiated support based on their individual requirements. Offer a variety of professional development opportunities that cater to different learning styles, experience levels, and subject areas. By providing differentiated support, the district can ensure that all teachers receive the necessary resources and guidance to meet their specific professional development needs

5. Foster collaborative learning communities: Create collaborative learning communities where teachers can engage in peer-to-peer learning and share best practices. Establish professional learning communities (PLCs), grade-level or subject-area teams, and regular opportunities for collaboration and reflection. Collaborative learning communities provide a platform for teachers to learn from one another, exchange ideas, and collectively improve their teaching practices.

6. Implement mentoring and coaching programs: Implement mentoring and coaching programs to support the professional growth of teachers. Experienced teachers can serve as mentors or coaches to provide guidance, feedback, and support to their colleagues. Mentoring and coaching relationships can help teachers refine their teaching practices, navigate challenges, and develop new skills.

7. Ensure ongoing support and resources: Ensure that teachers have access to ongoing support and resources to facilitate their professional development. This can include providing instructional materials, technology tools, research-based resources, and opportunities for continued learning. Ongoing support and resources will enable teachers to stay updated with current pedagogical approaches and enhance their teaching practices

8. Regularly evaluate and reflect: Regularly evaluate the effectiveness of the faculty development initiatives and encourage teachers to engage in reflection on their professional growth. Collect feedback from teachers, conduct self-assessments, and use data to inform future professional development efforts. Evaluation and reflection will help

identify areas of success and areas for improvement within the faculty development framework

By implementing a localized framework that incorporates these recommendations, Alilem District can provide targeted and effective support for teachers' professional development. This framework will empower teachers to enhance their teaching **practices** to stay updated with current pedagogical approaches and enhance their teaching practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research study, I, the author, affirm my adherence to the highest ethical standards. I hereby declare that:

All participants were fully informed about the nature and objectives of the study before their participation. I obtained informed consent from each participant, ensuring they understood their rights and the scope of the study.

In this study was entirely voluntary. All respondents were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

I have maintained the anonymity and confidentiality of all participants. Personal identifiers have been removed or masked to protect participants' privacy.

The well-being and safety of the participants were paramount throughout the study. Measures were taken to minimize any potential risks or discomfort to participants.

I declare that there is no conflict of interest that could have influenced the conduct or the results of the study. The research was conducted objectively and impartially.

I have strictly avoided plagiarism. All sources of information and data have been appropriately cited, and the work presented is original and authentic.

I have conducted this study with an unbiased approach. The interpretation of the findings was made without prejudice, and care was taken to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the results.

The results of this study have been used purely for research purposes. They are intended to contribute to the academic community's understanding of the subject matter and are not used for any commercial benefit.

By making this declaration, I affirm my commitment to conducting research that is ethically sound and responsible. I understand the importance of ethical standards in research and have endeavored to uphold these principles throughout my study.

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